

BASELINE STUDY

Empowerment of Fisherwomen in Coastal Chattogram and Cox's Bazar (EFCCC)

Conducted by

BRIGHT BANGLADESH FORUM

With the support of

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Bright Bangladesh Forum with the support of Oxfam and European Union has undertaken a project “Empowerment of Fisherwomen in Coastal Chattogram and Cox’s Bazar (EFCCC)” aiming to protect and promote social and legal rights and entitlements of marginalized working women in fisher folks and fishery sector in coastal areas of Chattogram and Cox’s Bazar district. This baseline study has been conducted as part of the project for in-depth understanding of socio-economic and human rights, especially gender-based violence, situation of the women in the fisher folk in Chattogram and Cox’s Bazar.

The baseline study design was a cross-sectional study comprised of both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Methods used included sample survey, observation, transect walk, focus group discussions and key informant interviews.

The study found high rate of illiteracy among the studied women with 21.75% of the participants could not sign and 60.75% could sign only. Fisherwomen were engaged in a varied range of fishery activities, majority (84.5%) of them were engaged in fish processing and more than half of them engaged (54.5%) in dry fish farm. The households of the surveyed women had an average annual income of BDT 120,381 and the women themselves had an average annual income of 54,929. 95.25% of the women reported that they do not get equal wages at their workplace as their male colleagues for the same occupation.

The study found a high perceived prevalence of gender-based violence 70.25% of the participants shared that either they themselves or their close friend/family members ever experienced gender-based violence in the last 12 months. Gender-based violence takes place at all level – at community level (58.75%), at household level (44.5%), outside the community (41.5%) and at workplace (28.25%). 89.25% of the respondents saw an early marriage in their families. However, now-a-days in many communities the early marriage incidences are gradually declining with increase in law enforcement and social restrictions. 82.75% of the surveyed women expressed that their families were engaged in either giving or asking for dowry during marriage. 71.25% reported that GBV took place at their families in relation to the dowry.

The survey found that, only 34% of respondents said they would seek support if they experienced gender-based violence. Using a scale of 10, the study found that 97.25% of the respondents had poor knowledge on their human, legal and health rights (scored below 06).

1. INTRODUCTION

Fishing and related activities are considered to be the domain of men in Bangladesh, particularly in coastal regions, and women's contributions to this sector are grossly undervalued. In fishery sector, women are mostly involved in sorting and grading fishes, transporting, selling and drying fishes. They also get engaged in collecting firewood and seashells. Many of their works remain unpaid and underpaid. There are social and religious norms persisting among fisherfolk compounded with higher rate of illiteracy limits the economic opportunity for women in fisher folks. High rate of early marriage is still seen in fisher folks and women often have very limited participation at family and social decision making. They often face gender-based violence at their home, at their community and at workplaces, including physical assault and sexual harassment. However, often they do not seek justice or legal support; and many of the violence remain unreported. There also exists discriminatory rules against women in fishery sector, for instance women are often paid 25 – 50%^{1,2} less than their counterpart male workers. Fisherwomen also face many occupational hazards at their work, e.g. musculoskeletal diseases due to heavy weight bearing, cut/sharp injuries, skin conditions etc. In summary, working women in fisher folk and fishing society often encounters gender-based violence and discriminations and occupational hazards.

Bright Bangladesh Forum with the support of Oxfam and European Union has undertaken a project “Empowerment of Fisherwomen in Coastal Chattogram and Cox’s Bazar (EFCCC)” aiming to protect and promote social and legal rights and entitlements of marginalized working women in fisher folks and fishery sector in coastal areas of Chattogram and Cox’s Bazar district through greater awareness and insitutional setup among fisherwomen, promotion of occupational safety, enhanced influence on policy making and greater access to legal support. This baseline study has been conducted as part of the project for in-depth understanding of socio-economic and human rights, especially gender-based violence, situation of the women in the fisher folk in the target areas in Chattogram and Cox’s Bazar.

Objectives of the study

Aim of the study was to provide baseline information on the socio-economic and gender-based violence situation in fisher folks in Cox’s Bazar and Chattogram. The specific objectives of the study were:

- (1) To explore the demographic and socio-economic situation of the women in the fisher folks.
- (2) To find out the perceived prevalence, type and causes of gender-based violence against the fisherwomen and identify the status of response to GBV.
- (3) To measure the level of knowledge among the women in the fisher folk on their human, legal and health rights.

¹ **COAST TRUST (2020)**. Women from Coastal Fishing Families are Suffering from Socio-economic Inequalities. Available at: <https://coastbd.net/women-from-coastal-fishing-families-are-suffering-from-socio-economic-inequalities/>

² **BBF (2022)**. Rapid situation analysis: women in fishery sector in Chattogram and Cox’s Bazar.

2. STUDY METHODOLOGY

The baseline study design was a cross-sectional study comprised of both qualitative and quantitative approaches aimed at collecting and analyzing data on the perception, knowledge, experience and skills of the fisherfolk women, the community people and the key stakeholders. The quantitative method included a sample survey with fisherfolk women and a qualitative methods included a range of participatory tools including preliminary assessment through observation, transect walk and random discussion with community stakeholders, two focus group discussions with fisher folk communities and eight key informant interviews with social and religious leaders, local government, line departments and NGOs.

Sample survey with women in fisher folks: The study team conducted a survey with fisher folk women using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire form was deployed through kobo toolbox for data collection. The questionnaire was developed based on the indicators mentioned in the logical framework of the project and comprised of indicators on demographic profile, socio-economic status, gender-based violence situation and knowledge level on human, legal and health rights. The questionnaire was initially piloted with 10 participants, and adjustments were made as needed in the final version depending on the results of the testing.

The survey was conducted among a sample size of 400 women, proportionately distribution in four target locations of the project – Jaliapalong, Samity para-Najiratek and Choufoldondi in Cox’s Bazar and Fisheryghat in Chattogram. The women were randomly selected – 10 from each sub-locations totaling 100 from each location - from the project beneficiary list prepared earlier by the community facilitators. While, using 95% confidence level, the sample size of the study should be 385, the study had the sample size of 400. The community facilitators collected the data using kobo toolbox form and submitted online.

Focus group discussion: 2 focus group discussions were conducted by the study team – one at Jaliapalong, Ukhiya and one at Fisheryghat Chattagram, to get in depth understanding of the socio-economic and gender situation in the fisher folk communities and triangulate the findings from the quantitative method. At each FGD, 10 fishermen and women were actively engaged in the discussion. Participatory approaches and creative interview techniques were applied to promote active participation. A semi-structured guiding questionnaire was used for guiding the discussion. Project Manager, Project Officer and Community Facilitators facilitated the FGDs and recorded the data.

Key informant interview: As part of the qualitative approach, eight key informant interviews were facilitated with fishery sector officials, local government representatives, fishery business, social and religious leaders and local NGO representatives. A semi-structured questionnaire was used for guiding the data collection. Project Manager and Project Officer facilitated the interviews and recorded the data.

Quantitative data were analyzed using kobo-toolbox in-built analysis tool as well as Microsoft excel. Qualitative data were transcribed verbatim and analyzed manually using thematic analysis approach.

Photo: Naziratek-Samiti Para

3. STUDY LOCATION:

The study was implemented in fishermen colonies in Cox's Bazar and Chattogram. Table 3.1 shows a detailed overview of the study location.

The Naziratek-Samiti Para and Choufoldoni areas are home to a substantial number of coastal fishing settlements. The main sources of income in these areas are tied to fishing and fish processing. Fishermen are engaged in fishing from the deep Bay of Bengal. The largest dry fish processing zone in the country is located at Naziratek-Samitipara, which accommodates hundreds of dry fish processing trades. In addition to fishing from the sea, there are also a number of private fishing farms in Choufoldoni. The area is also inhabited by indigenous Rakhaine community. A traditional delicacy of the indigenous people, powdered dry fish (also known as nappi locally), is prepared here and exported to the indigenous populations in various districts of Bangladesh.

Around the Firingibazar, Patharghata, and Bokshirhat areas by the river Karnaphull in Chattogram, fishing communities have grown. The main sources of income for those living in the colonies are fishing, fish processing, and involvement in the fisheries industry.

Table 3.1: Location of the study

District	Upazila/City Corporation	Union/City wards	Villages/Wards
Cox's Bazar	Cox's Bazar Sadar Upazila	Cox's Bazar Pouroshova	Najiratek Samiti Para Bashinda Para Sutki Mohal Mostak para North and Middle Kutubdiya para
		Choufoldondi Union Parishad	1 no ward North Rakhaine Para 2 no. ward south para 4 no ward west para
	Ukhiya Upazila	Jaliyapalong Union	3 no ward North Sonapara 4 no ward Dail para 5 no ward small Inani Middle Nidaniya 7 no ward Jaliya palong
Chattogram	Chattogram City Corporation	CCC Wards – 33,34,35 (Firingibazar-Patharghata- Bokshirhat)	Firingi Bazar Loittaghata Fisharighat Bastuhara

4. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

4.1 Demographic profile of the study participants:

4.1.1 Age, sex and location: A total of 400 women participated in responding to the quantitative survey questionnaire. Average age of the respondents was 40.76 and median age was 38.50. 74.25% of the respondents were from Cox's Bazar and rest were from Chattogram. A union wise distribution of the participants is shown in **Table 4.1**.

Table 4.1 Location-wise distribution of the participants

Upazila	Union	# of participants	Percentage
Cox's Bazar Sadar	Cox's Bazar Pouroshova	128	32%
Cox's Bazar Sadar	Choufoldondi Union	69	17.25%
Ukhiya	Jaliyapalong Union	99	24.75%
Chattogram City Corporation	Firingibazar-patharghata-Bokshirhat ward	104	26%

4.1.2 Family type: Three fourth of the participants lived in single/nuclear family (75.25%) and a quarter (24.75%) were from joint families.

4.1.3 Education: Fisher folk communities are prevalent with low level of literacy. Illiteracy rate was found very high among the survey participants. 21.75% of the participants could not sign and 60.75% could sign only. Only 10.5% of the surveyed women studied upto class V and 6.25% studied lower secondary. Only 0.5% completed secondary school (SSC). None of the participants studied beyond SSC.

Chart 4.1. Level of literacy among women participated in the study

4.2 Socio-Economic Situation:

4.2.1 Housing Status:

The fisherwomen with their families lives usually in overcrowded village homes made of bamboo, grass or corrugated iron sheets. The survey found that half of the respondents (50%) were living in their owned house and around a quarter (23.5%) were living in rented house. 6.75% lived free of cost with neighbor. In some areas (e.g. Samiti para), although the fishermen families own the houses, the lands are usually *khas* (government owned fallow lands).

Chart 4.2 Housing status of the families of the studied fisherwomen

4.2.2 Source of water for drinking and household chores:

More than half of the participants (56.75%) had access to deep tube well for drinking water and 29.25% used shallow tubewell. 13.5% were dependent on supply water. 0.5% of the respondents reported getting drinking water from ponds. For use in household chores 40.5% of the participants reported using shallow tubewell and 38.25% reported using deep tubewell. Use of river/canal (8.25%) and ponds (7%) were also reported. 6% were dependent on supplied water.

Chart 4.3 Source of drinking water for the families of studied fisherwomen

Chart 4.4 Source of water for household chores for the families of studied fisherwomen

4.2.3 Safety concern of women while fetching, collecting and/or transporting water:
 37.5% of the surveyed women reported about safety concern for women while they fetch/collect and/or transport water.

Chart 4.5 Women reporting safety concern while collecting and/or transporting water

4.2.4 Type of toilets:

37.50% of the households were found having a sanitary latrine. 38% of the families had slab with ring and 18.25% had private closed pits. Private open pit (3.50%), slab without ring (1.25%), communal closed pits (0.75%) and the practice of open defecation (0.50%) were also observed.

Chart 4.6 Type of toilets used by the families of studied women

4.2.5 Occupation:

The fisher folk communities' work in a variety of fishery-related livelihoods, primarily connected to fishing from the sea, selling fish, drying fish, and processing and chopping fish. In the seashore colonies, commonly, men goes for fishing in the deep sea and the women collect, sort out, grade, sell and dry fishes. While in some areas, like Najiratek, women are formally employed in fishery economic activities (such as manual labor for dry fish), in others, like Fisheryghat, women support their husbands in fishing companies and activities. In Choufoldondi men and women are also found engaged in producing dry fish powder or *Nappi*. Irrespective of their engagement in the economic activities, women in the fisherfolk are obligated to do household chores including cooking and child care in addition to participating in fishing activities.

Photo: women engaged in fish processing

The survey found that fisherwomen were engaged in a varied range of fishery activities. One person might engaged in multiple fishery or non-fishery activities. Majority (84.5%) of them were engaged in fish processing and more than half of them engaged (54.5%) in dry fish farm. 33% of them were involved in fish cutting and 29.75% were involved in fish grading. 11% of the women were engaged in powder dry fish (*Nappi*) processing, they are mainly from the Choufoldondi area. Women were also engaged in daily labor in fishery (10.75%), fishing (6.25%), transporting fish/dry fish (5.75%), selling fish/dry fish (2.25%), fish marketing (2%), ice processing (2%), net making (1.5%), fish whole sale activity (0.75%), basket making (0.5%) and boat driving (0.25%). Additionally, 40% of the women were also involved in non-fishery activities, a few worked in big (0.5%) and small shops (0.25%).

During off season (when fishing is prohibited), women are also engaged in collecting minnow and seashells from the sea shores and wood pieces from the hills.

Table 4.2 Type of economic activities fisherwomen engaged in

Activities engaged in (multiple activities per person possible)	Frequency	Percentage
Fish processing	338	84.5
Dry fish farm work	217	54.25
Other non-fishery activity	160	40
Fish cutting	132	33
Fish grading	119	29.75
Other fishery activity	59	14.75
Powder dry fish (Nappi) processing	44	11
Daily labour in fishery	43	10.75
Fishing	25	6.25
Transporting fish/dry fish	23	5.75
Selling fish/dry fish	9	2.25
Marketing	8	2
Ice processing	8	2
Net making	6	1.5
Fish wholesale activity (aarat)	3	0.75
Basket making	2	0.5
Big shop	2	0.5
Small shop	1	0.25
Boat man	1	0.25

While majority (67.75%) of the women were engaged in direct manual works, 23.75% owned they economic activity. A few (0.75%) were engaged in leading role (e.g. Majhi).

Chart 4.7 Role of women in economic activities

4.2.6 Occupation of the family head:

Family heads of the participants were also found engaged in range of fishery activities, including fish processing (50%), fishing (35.25%), boat man (27.75%), dry fish farm works (25.5%), fish grading (17.5%), fish cutting (15.75%), daily labor in fishery (13.75%), net making (9.5%), powder dry fish (Napping) processing (9.5%), selling fish/dry fish (4.5%), marketing (1.75%), fish wholesale (aarot) activity (1%), ice processing (1%), basket making (0.25%) and other fishery activities (15.5%). 44.25% had also engagement in non-fishery activity.

Table 4.3 Type of economic activities fisherwomen engaged in

Value	Frequency	Percentage
Fish processing	200	50
Other non-fishery activity	177	44.25
Fishing	141	35.25
Boat man	111	27.75
Dry fish farm work	102	25.5
Fish grading	70	17.5
Fish cutting	63	15.75
Other fishery activity	62	15.5
Daily labour in fishery	55	13.75
Net making	38	9.5
Powder dry fish (Nappi) processing	38	9.5
Selling fish/dry fish	18	4.5
Transporting fish/dry fish	11	2.75
Boat owner	8	2
Marketing	7	1.75
Fish wholesale activity (aarot)	4	1
Ice processing	4	1
Basket making	1	0.25
Small shop	1	0.25

4.2.7 Annual Income:

The households of the surveyed women had an average annual income of BDT 120,381, while the median income was BDT 96,000 and mode of the annual income was 120,000. The interviewed women themselves had an average annual income of 54,929. The median of their annual income was 48,000 and the mode was BDT 30,000.

Table 4.4 Central tendency of annual income of the women and their families

Central Tendency	Family annual income	Annual income of the women
Mean	120381.00	54929.90
Median	96000.00	48000.00
Mode	120000.00	30000.00

Photo: Women working at the dry fish processing farms

4.2.8 Equality of wages at workplace:

95.25% of the women reported that they do not get equal wages at their workplace as their male colleagues for the same occupation. The reason often explained for this inequality is men usually takes heavier loads in comparison to women.

Table 4.5 Status of equality of wages at workplace

Expression on getting equal wages	Frequency	Percentage
No	381	95.25%
Yes	19	4.75%

4.2.9 Possession of a bank account:

Only 17.75% participants had a bank account and 83.75 did not have any.

4.2.10 Participation in groups/organization:

85% of the participants reported that they were not part of any organization or community-based group.

Table 4.6 Status of the women in relation to their participation in groups/organization

Participation in groups/organization	Frequency	Percentage
No	340	85
Yes	58	14.5

4.3 Gender-based violence

4.3.1 Perceived prevalence of gender-based violence:

While it was ethically challenging to find out the actual prevalence of gender-based violence in the community, the study explored the experience of the participants either related to themselves or their close friend/family members so that the identity of the actual victims were not revealed. 70.25% of the participants shared that either they themselves or their close friend/family members ever experienced gender-based violence in the last 12 months.

Table 4.7: Perceived prevalence of gender-based violence (experience in relation to self or close friend/family member)

Experienced a GBV (self or friend/family)	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	281	70.25
No	119	29.75

4.3.2 Place where GBV took place:

Gender-based violence takes place at all level – at community level (58.75%), at household level (44.5%), outside the community (41.5%) and at workplace (28.25%).

Chart 4.8. Place where GBV incident/s took place: Type of GBV incidents:

4.3.3 Type of GBV incidents at household Level:

Although domestic violence is a common incidence, this usually remains unreported. Type of GBV incidents reported by the participants at household level experienced either by themselves or their close friend/family members include minor physical assault (22.75%), sexual assault (18.25%), verbal insult or harassment (17.25%), defamation (16.75%), serious physical assault (15.75%), early marriage (14.75%), sexual harassment (13.75%), coercion (9.5%), manslaughter (7.5%), incompletion to economic responsibilities (6.5%), abduction (6%), rape (4.75%), restriction of access to financial resources (4%), property damage (3%), trafficking (3%), restriction of access to education (2.75%), restriction of movement outside the home (2%), restriction of access to labour market (1%) and others (15.5%).

Table 4.8 Type of GBV incident the participant reported in relation to the experience of themselves or their close friend/family members have experienced in the last 12 months at the household:

Type of GBV incidents reported at household level	Frequency of report	Percentage of participants
Minor physical assault	91	22.75
Sexual assault	73	18.25
Verbal insult or harassment	69	17.25
Defamation	67	16.75
Serious physical assault	63	15.75
Others	62	15.5
Early marriage	59	14.75
Sexual harassment	55	13.75
Coercion	38	9.5
Manslaughter	30	7.5
Do not comply with economic responsibilities	26	6.5
Abduction	24	6
Rape	19	4.75
Restricting access to financial resources	16	4
Property damage	12	3
Trafficking	12	3
Restricting access to education	11	2.75
Restricting movement outside the home	8	2
Restricting access to labour market	4	1

4.3.4 Type of GBV incidents at workplace Level:

Type of GBV incidents reported by the participants at workplace level experienced either by themselves or their close friend/family members include serious physical assault (17%), sexual assault (17%), early marriage (14.5%), sexual harassment (14.25%), minor physical assault (12%), defamation (11%), abduction (10.25%), manslaughter (10%), verbal insult or harassment (9.5%), coercion (9%), rape (5.75%), property damage (4%), trafficking (3.25%), over workload in comparison to men (3%), restricting access to financial resources (2.75%), less paid in comparison to men (2%) and others (9%).

Table 4.9 Type of GBV incident the participant reported in relation to the experience of themselves or their close friend/family members have experienced in the last 12 months at workplace:

Type of GBV incidents reported at workplace	Frequency	Percentage
Serious physical assault	68	17
Sexual assault	68	17
Early marriage	58	14.5
Sexual harassment	57	14.25
Minor physical assault	48	12
Defamation	44	11
Abduction	41	10.25
Manslaughter	40	10
Verbal insult or harassment	38	9.5
Other	36	9
Coercion	36	9
Rape	23	5.75
Property damage	16	4
Trafficking	13	3.25
Over workload in comparison to men	12	3
Restricting access to financial resources	11	2.75
Less paid in comparison to men	8	2

4.3.5 Type of GBV incidents at community or outside the community:

Type of GBV incidents reported by the participants at their community or outside the community experienced either by themselves or their close friend/family members include Minor physical assault (43.5%), sexual harassment (42.5%), early marriage (41.25%), verbal insult or harassment (36.75%), defamation (35%), sexual assault (34.5%), serious physical assault (22.25%), less payment in comparison to men (16.75%), coercion (11%), abduction (9.75%), manslaughter (9.75%), rape (7%), trafficking (5.5%), restricting access to education (5%), restricting access to financial resources (3.25%), property damage (3.25%), giving over workload in comparison to men (2.5%) and others (13.75%). 240 out of 400 respondents answered this question.

Table 4.10 Type of GBV incident the participant reported in relation to the experience of themselves or their close friend/family members have experienced in the last 12 months at own community or outside the community:

Type of GBV incidents reported at own community/outside the community	Frequency	Percentage
Minor physical assault	174	43.5
Sexual harassment	170	42.5
Early marriage	165	41.25
Verbal insult or harassment	147	36.75
Defamation	140	35
Sexual assault	138	34.5
Serious physical assault	89	22.25
Less paid in comparison to men	67	16.75
Other	55	13.75
Coercion	44	11
Abduction	39	9.75
Manslaughter	39	9.75
Rape	28	7
Trafficking	22	5.5
Restricting access to education	20	5
Restricting access to financial resources	13	3.25
Property damage	13	3.25
Restricting access to financial resources	13	3.25
Over workload in comparison to men	10	2.5

4.3.6 Perpetrators of GBV:

Majority of the participants, 66.7%, reported that muscle men of the society were commonly responsible for the gender-based violence and nearly half (47.75%) reported about the stalkers. 38.25% reported that the intimate partners (38.35%) were involved in the violence. Respondents also reported about their family members, including the mothers (27.25%), fathers (23%), brothers (6%), and in law family members, including mothers in law (12%) and fathers in law (9%).

Table 4.11 Perpetrators of GBV opined by the women

Reported perpetrator	Frequency	Percentage
Muscle men	267	66.75
Stalker	191	47.75
Others	159	39.75
Husband/partner	153	38.25
Mother	109	27.25
Father	92	23
Mother in law	48	12
Father in law	36	9
Brother	24	6

4.3.7 Reasons behind gender-based violence

88.75% of the participated women believed that poverty is the main cause behind the GBV. 59.25% of the women blamed the behavior of the men as the cause. More than half of the respondents expressed lack of legal support (53%) and lack of education as the causes of GBV. Nearly half of the women (47%) identified dowry system in the society as one of the causes of GBV. Other causes identified include lack of platform for women (24%), lack of women voice (21.25%), lack of law enforcement (19%) and alcohol (16.5%).

Table 4.12 Reasons behind gender-based violence identified by the women

Value	Frequency	Percentage
Poverty	355	88.75
Behaviour of man	237	59.25
Lack of legal support	212	53
Lack of education	201	50.25
Dowry	188	47
Lack of women platform	96	24
Lack of women voice	85	21.25
Lack of law enforcement	76	19
Alcohol	66	16.5
Others	61	15.25

4.3.8 Early marriage:

89.25% of the respondents saw an early marriage in their families. However, now-a-days in many communities the early marriage incidences are gradually declining with increase law enforcement and social restrictions. In some folks, early marriage happens among both boys and girls. In many families early marriage of girls is encouraged since value of dowry may rise of the bride gets older.

Table 4.13 Experience of the surveyed women on early marriage at their family

Experienced early marriage	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	358	89.5
No	37	9.25

4.3.9 Dowry:

Dowry is pervasively common among the fisher folks, it is usually impossible to have a marriage without dowry from the bride's family. Cash money, furniture and electronic items (e.g. freeze, television) are usually claimed as dowry. As the bride gets older, the value of the dowry rises. 82.75% of the surveyed women expressed that their families were engaged in either giving or asking for dowry during marriage. 71.25% of the women reported that GBV took place at their families in relation to the dowry.

Table 4.14 Experience of the women about their family in giving or asking for dowry during marriage:

Experience of giving or asking dowry at their family	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	331	82.75
No	69	17.25

Table 4.15 Incident of gender-based violence at family in relation to dowry:

Incident of GBV in relation to Dowry	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	287	71.75
No	110	27.5

4.3.10 Response from the community during an incident of gender-based violence:

Majority of the women (86.5%) reported that people usually blame women in the event of a gender-based violence. Other responses included remaining silent (53.5%), blaming men (40.25%), raising voice (20%), supporting the victim (17.25%) and supporting the perpetrator (16.5%).

Table 4.16 Usual response from the community during an incident of gender-based violence:

Value	Frequency	Percentage
People blame women	346	86.5
People remain silent	214	53.5
People blame men	161	40.25
People raise their voice	80	20
Others	71	17.75
People support the victim	69	17.25
People support the perpetrator	66	16.5

4.3.11 Seeking support in case of GBV:

Incidents of GBV usually remain unreported because of the fear of social harassment, lack of awareness and fear of further harm. In intolerable or extreme cases, women reports to local leaders (e.g. Sardar) for mediation. In rare cases, the elected councilor office is reached for mediation support. There is almost no mechanism in place at workplace of fishery sector for prevention of and respond to gender-based violence. The survey found that, only 34% of respondents said they would seek support if they experienced gender-based violence, leaving 65.25% of respondents to say they would not.

Table 4.17 Opinion of the women whether they would report of seek support if they experience GBV

Seek support/report	Frequency	Percentage
No	261	65.25
Yes	136	34

Causes of behind not seeking support includes feeling shame (18%), fear of separation or divorce (14.75%), fear of stigma (11.25%), lack of available information (5.5%), fear of losing job (5.25%), threat of further violence (4.5%), lack of available support (3.5%) and fear of isolation (2%).

Table 4.18 Reasons for not reporting or seeking support in case of GBV

Value	Frequency	Percentage
Feeling shame	72	18
Fear of separation or divorce	59	14.75
Fear of stigma	45	11.25
Lack of information available	22	5.5
Fear of losing job	21	5.25
Threat of further violence	18	4.5
Lack of support available	14	3.5
Fear of isolation	8	2
Other	1	0.25

4.4 Knowledge of the women on their human, legal and health rights:

As part of the survey, an assessment of the knowledge level of the women on their human, legal and health rights was conducted. The participants were asked 10 questions linked on human, legal and health rights and their response (correct/incorrect) were recorded. In a scale of 10, we considered an achieved score of 6 or more as good level knowledge. Using this scale 97.25% of the respondents had poor knowledge on their human, legal and health rights. A detailed breakdown of their achieved score is demonstrated in the table 4.19.

Table 4.19 Achieved score of the women at the assessment of their knowledge on their human, legal and health rights

Gained Score	Number of Participants	Percentage of total participants
0	131	32.75%
1	39	9.75%
2	48	12.00%
3	52	13.00%
4	87	21.75%
5	32	8.00%
6	1	0.25%
7	4	1.00%
8	3	0.75%
9	2	0.50%
10	1	0.25%
Total	400	100.00%

Chart 4.9 Distribution of the women in a knowledge scale (of 10) on human, legal and health rights

94.25% of the women did not have correct perception on the equal rights of men and women rights in different spheres of service and public life. More than half of the respondents (52.25%) did not know the legal age of marriage for girls in Bangladesh. Around half of the women (49.25%) did not consider giving, taking or demanding of dowry as a crime. 71.5% did not correctly know the legal consequence of rape, sexual exploitation for gain, abduction, kidnapping or attempt to cause the death of a woman. A majority of the women did not have correct understanding of rights of women to education (93.75%), own property (81.75%) and right to vote (87.75%). 98.75% of the women did not believe that men and women should have equal wages at workplace for same position/similar work. 57.5% of the women did not know that regarding the obligation of the employer for health and safety of the employees at workplace. Nearly 90% of the women did not know about their rights of women to determine the number and spacing of their children (including contraceptives).

Table 4.20 Response of the women in questions regarding human, legal and health rights

Knowledge on human, legal and health rights	Correctly responded to relevant question	Incorrectly responded to relevant question
Equal rights of men and women rights in different spheres of service and public life	5%	94.25%
Legal age of marriage for girls in Bangladesh	47.25%	52.5%

Knowledge on human, legal and health rights	Correctly responded to relevant question	Incorrectly responded to relevant question
Giving, taking or demanding of a dowry	50.5%	49.25%
legal consequence of rape, sexual exploitation for gain, abduction, kidnapping or attempt to cause the death of a woman	28.25	71.5
Equal rights of men and women for education	5.75%	93.75%
Right of women to own property	18.25%	81.75%
Rights of women to vote	11.5%	87.75%
Equal wages for men and women at workplace for same position/similar work	1%	98.75%
Responsibility of employer for health and safety at workplace	42.25%	57.5%
Rights of women to determine the number and spacing of their children (including contraceptives)	11%	88.75%

4.5 Other challenges:

Following other challenges were identified for the fisherwomen through the qualitative methods.

- Due to patriarchal social norms, women have limited voice and participation in family and social decision making.
- Women often face occupation health hazards, like back pains due to carrying heavy loads, hand injuries and wounds during sorting out fishes, urinary complications due to limited arrangement of toilets at workplace. The workplace is often unhygienic and unhealthy.
- Lactating women needs to carry their babies at workplace, however, there is no separate space available for breastfeeding
- Women do not get support and payment from the employer if they are sick,
- Managing domestic responsibilities and economic activity at the same time is frequently tough for the women.

5. CONCLUSION

The study revealed the socio-economic and gender-based violence situation of the women in the fisher folks in Cox's Bazar and Chattogram. While the study found an extensive engagement of women in fishing and fishery-related activities, it revealed the high prevalence of gender-based violence to the women in the fisherfolks at all levels, including at household level, at and outside the community and at their workplaces. The study also identified the poor level of knowledge among the women on their human, legal and health rights and entitlements. Limited mechanisms are in place to provide legal protection and support to the survivors of gender-based violence or to prevent such incidences at community and workplaces. An integrated effort is required aware the women on their human and legal rights and entitlements, mobilize the community for promoting gender equality and preventing gender-based violence, undertaking and implementing proper policies and actions for protection and safety of women at their home, community and workplace and enhancing access of the women to legal services.

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